

INDIVIDUALIZED READING INTERVENTION FOR STRUGGLING READERS: CHRONICLES OF TEACHERS' REFLECTIONS

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Abstract. This study aimed to help reading teachers handle individualized reading intervention programs for struggling readers beset with problematic situations that, when not properly understood, can bring detriment to the reading progress of children with specific reading difficulties. This phenomenological inquiry on the lived experiences of reading teachers handling face-to-face, one-on-one reading instruction for struggling readers was conducted with 10 elementary reading teachers to explore their experiences towards giving individualized intervention. This study revealed that reading teachers handling individualized instruction face the following challenges: low motivation and engagement, lack of professional development, and less parental involvement; while coping mechanisms they adopted, namely, the reading teachers exhibited patience and empathy, used differentiation in reading instruction, and incorporated technology in handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers. Among the educational insights that the participant underscored include individual differences deemed crucial, early intervention as indispensable, and parental and community involvement as necessary in successfully implementing the individualized reading intervention for struggling readers. Implications drawn from the study's conclusions include institutionalizing capacity-building programs to empower reading teachers and seeking assistance from the community and stakeholders for schools to implement reading programs and augment readers' progress fully.

KEY WORDS

1. Struggling learners
2. individualized reading intervention
3. teachers' experiences

1. Introduction

Reading interventions are critical in supporting struggling readers and helping them improve their reading skills. Individual interventions are one-on-one instruction tailored to meet the specific needs of individual students. These interventions are ideally conducted in the lowest grades possible. However, even later-grade interventions can be effective. A gesture of support for implementing inclusive education was to carry out instruction to address a learner's specific learning needs. The instruction may be modified by switching from regular instruction to differentiating or individualizing teaching. This, too, is applicable in the context of teaching reading, as teachers almost always deal with learners who manifest reading prob-

lems. Although trained professionally regarding individualized or differentiated instruction, it is undeniable that reading teachers go through difficult times in employing teaching strategies to address learners' reading problems. This predicament that reading teachers have to deal with may be seen as reading teachers failing to close the achievement gaps among readers. In the United States of America, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) reported that the reading proficiency of the fourth, eighth, and twelfth graders in school districts across the United States has only achieved a marginal increase. This goes to show that the impact of the reading intervention programs that the district schools run may have been inadequate as they fail to bring forth a significant increase in the reading performance of readers, implying further that individualized reading intervention may have been incorporated in the program but has not been that comprehensive and operational given the number of learners that struggle in reading (Deallio, 2020). Thus, Spector (2018) argued that a personalized learning environment should be adaptive to individual knowledge, experience, and interests to effectively and efficiently promote reading skills in the context of individualized reading intervention. With all these that ideally must constitute the requirements for an effective and efficient reading program, school administrators, reading coordinators, and reading teachers are confronted with these challenges, especially in the light of individualizing reading instruction to operationalize an individualized reading intervention. While it is almost always inevitable that these necessities are not met, reading teachers may also encounter other problems with which they have less or no control; however, they are generally purpose-driven, and these hurdles in implementing individualized reading instruction are overcome in the long run. On the other hand, in South Africa, the government, in general, has shown frustration and disappointment that people who are engaged and working in the education sector have failed to improve learners' performance, especially in the literacy sub-sector. According to Spaul (2019), the education sector has gone through a stalling phase as literacy performance in most schools shows delays based on the 2011 to 2016 data. In this regard, the PIRLS 2016 results reveal the literacy crisis ringing a bell to the academic communities and learning institutions nationwide. The data also indicate that intervention and remediation programs, which may have been espoused in teaching reading, are generally unable to address learning performance gaps in promoting literacy in the region. In Bangkok, Thailand, a research finding reported by Vibulpatanavong and Evans (2019) revealed the need to teach beginning readers in Thai as the nature of the Thai language may not be as transparent as previously thought. Further, the finding unraveled that to improve the identification of reading difficulties in Thai language, systematic investigation of the nature of Thai language and how beginning reading instruction is taught in Thailand are needed. This is an indication that the number of struggling readers that need individualized reading intervention in the Thai context needed integration in the intervention of the use of the native tongue to build foundational skills in reading, as this is identified as the probable cause for the reading problem. In the Philippine context of the education system, students from low-income families tend to put work first at an early age instead of formal schooling. Poverty and lack of academic resources also affect their cognitive development and socialization with people in the academe. A child surrounded by teachers, books, or any reading materials has a clear vision of the importance of education. The survey also shows that the Philippines ranked second to the lowest in Science and Mathematics (Meron, 2018). In the Philippines, the general reading performance of Filipino learners is relatively higher

than that of any other Asian country, as reported by Business World (2020); however, at the fifth-grade level, it was found that the learners are falling behind their counterparts in some Southeast Asian countries in reading basing on the significant percentage of learners still at levels expected in early years of primary education. The data from the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 confirms this minimum proficiency level achieved in reading. Filipino learners' proficiency is significantly lower than that of Vietnamese and Malaysian learners. This decline in reading proficiency experienced in the Philippine education sector has seen the need to continuously sustain reading programs where individualization of the reading intervention is deemed necessary, as most of the detected reading problems are rooted in the individual needs and contexts surrounding each struggling reader. In The Philippines Star News Publication as reported by Chi(2024). At least 90 percent of Filipino children aged ten struggle to read or understand simple text, according to the World Bank's 2022 data on learning poverty. But even before the COVID-19 pandemic set back students' learning, the pre-pandemic figure pegged learning poverty in the Philippines at 70 percent. Ene 11, 2024. In Region XI, specifically in Davao Oriental, the reading programs implemented in the elementary schools in the division were adopting reading intervention programs in response to the assessed needs of learners who are struggling with reading. As the academic community sees the importance of reading in promoting academic achievement among learners, all concerned are partaking in activities that address the reading problems of learners. However, with the limitations of adopting intervention programs, particularly an individualized reading intervention, proficiency in reading would remain a challenge among educators. Individualizing reading instruction necessitates a teaching skill set composed of many teaching strategies and methodologies, allowing a teacher to pick which one fits the learning contexts of a learner. This was coupled with a wide range of reading materials, which the reading teacher prefers in consideration of the assessed reading level of a learner and the learning contexts where they are situated. When found inadequate within a reading program, these pose a challenge to the reading teacher, which eventually impacts the progress of a reading learner. Moreover, a learning environment also matters in assessing the outcomes of individualized instruction. With the preceding settings of the problem and the research gaps that need to be narrowed, the researcher pursues this study.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study explored the lived experiences of reading teachers facilitating an individualized reading intervention. The study shall specifically focus on the realities that these teachers have come across within the performance of this function in addition to the regular teaching loads with which they are engaged in the day-to-day duties and responsibilities as reading teachers. The study purposively explores the dimension of the conduct of individualized reading intervention as this is one of the commonly practiced means of addressing reading problems among struggling learners. Teaching them to read in groups would deter the detection of reading needs as these are specific to a reader. Exploring the lived experiences of reading teachers may lead to discovering both the challenges and the gains reading teachers have experienced, consciously and unconsciously, in the process. It shall also uncover their personal beliefs on and attitude towards individualizing the teaching of reading to struggling readers. The study's underlying assumption is the need to underscore their individual or collective beliefs and attitudes as elemental in improving the reading skills of struggling readers. Hence, the unifying element of the study is focused on the participants' reflections on their experiences in dealing with

the challenges and the rewards of their engagement with struggling readers in the context of individualized reading intervention.

- (1) What are teachers' challenges in individualized reading intervention for struggling readers?
- (2) How do the teachers cope with the challenges of individualized reading intervention for struggling readers?
- (3) What educational insight can be drawn forth from the lived experiences of reading teachers in individualized reading intervention?

1.2. *Theoretical Lens*—This study was anchored on the Zone of Proximal Development from the Social Learning Theory developed by Lev Vygotsky (1978). As theorized, the Zone of Proximal Development is defined as the distance between the actual development level as determined by independent problem-solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers. The theory further states that when a learner is in the zone of proximal development for a specific task, the provision of appropriate assistance or guidance is enough to boost the learner's confidence to achieve the task. The study is anchored to this theory in the light that the study explores the lived experiences of reading teachers implementing individualized reading intervention for struggling readers. Implementing so, the reading teachers are the ones that provide the guidance or the scaffolds so as to take the learner to a desired level in reading. The assistance therefore that is given by a reading teacher in the context of individualized reading intervention is believed to bring the struggling reader to a zone of proximal development. The study is also anchored on the learning and motivation theory, the Operant Conditioning which was developed by B.F. Skinner (1937). The theory posits that the use of reinforcement increases the likelihood that a response will occur. This reinforcement may come in a form of praise or any reward which can cause the learner to respond and perform the desired action. It claims further that the more this reinforcement is presented to the learner, the more he or she exhibits the desired behavior as having been motivated by the reinforcer. The

study uses this theory in the light that handling an individualized reading intervention involves motivating a struggling reader to strive harder as he or she is individually taught by the reading teacher. Furthermore, the reading problem that a struggling reader deals with is a state where motivation is deemed imperative so as to assist the child in the process. A struggling reader may be motivated to learn reading as rewards which may come in a form of praise, material reward or an assurance that his or her reading progress equates with academic gains, are presented to his or her. On the other hand, reading teachers who are implementers of individualized reading interventions need some kind of motivation, too, as they are posed with challenges and limitations in the conduct of this individualized reading instruction. Furthermore, this study is also anchored on the Theory of Ecological Systems by Bronfenbrenner (1970). The theory posits that child development is a complex system of relationships affected by multiple levels of the surrounding environment, from immediate settings of family and school to broad cultural values, laws and customs. The study relates so much with this theory inasmuch as individualized reading interventions is based on the idea of inclusive development, which further implies that putting a struggling reader in the program is a gesture of belief that development is for everybody; thus, a struggling reader's need must also be given a preferential attention by all concerned. The theory relates with the study on the grounds that when reading teachers adopt the individualized reading intervention, they have to understand the complex system of relationships

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

which may affect the development of a struggling reader. Thus, when the relationship provided by the learning environment is founded on concern for child’s development, it can be contributory to his or her advancement.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. As shown in the figure, there are three interconnected variables. The first

one is the challenges of reading teachers implementing individualized reading interventions for struggling readers; the second one is the coping mechanisms of reading teachers handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers; and the last one is educational insights drawn from the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. The exploration of the facts and knowledge that substantiate this study entails the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the conclusions and decisions. Elaborated below are the common philosophical assumptions that come in varied types: Ontology. This section of the research deals with the issues that relate to the nature of reality. Subscribing to the notion of Creswell (2012), I contend that reality was subjective and multiple as experienced by the participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualita-

tive researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals engaged in the research context. Expectedly, there shall be a number of realities that may exist. These realities of the research include those of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of reading teachers involved in implementing individualized reading intervention for struggling readers. On the other hand, I depended so much on the voices and interpretations of the research participants. This was done through the use of extensive quotes and themes that are reflective of their words and

provide pieces of evidence of varying points of view. The participant's responses to the questions shall be coded and analyzed to create and construct the commonality and discreteness of the responses. I shall ascertain that the participants' responses shall be painstakingly coded to guarantee the reliability of the results. Likewise, the researcher fosters the authenticity of the responses and refrains from making personal biases as the study was carried out. Epistemology. This philosophical assumption pertains to the awareness of the justification of knowledge claims by means of staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in the interest of obtaining first-hand data. This is consistent with the notion of Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempts to narrow the distance between himself or herself from the participants. An author also contends that as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' This study intended to understand how reading teachers go through the seemingly challenging work as he or she implement an individualized reading intervention. I shall conform to the guidelines set forth by the Department of Education (DepED) and other regulations with which the conduct of the study has to be governed with. It shall be ascertained

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—I particularly distinguish methodology from method. It was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the latter pertains to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In the context of this study, the lived experiences of reading teachers engaged in implementing individualized reading interventions for struggling readers. I intend to look into the participants' experiences' deeper meanings in handling an individualized reading intervention for struggling read-

ers. With such a research intention, I deemed it helpful that a specific research approach helps look for meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. Hence, I opted for the use of phenomenology for the intended research purpose. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two that close interaction with the participants is secured to elicit direct information that is expected to shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. This philosophical assumption pertains to the role of values in research. In this regard, Creswell (2012) posits that the role of values in a study is crucial. This assumption recommends that the researcher should openly take up values that give the narrative its shape and include their interpretation in collaboration with the interpretation of participants. Furthermore, the researcher shall promote the dignity and value of every bit of information elicited from the participants. The researcher likewise understands the personal and value-laden characteristics of the information gathered from the study. Hence, the researcher shall see to it that the participants' responses shall be painstakingly interpreted from the space of their interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption maintains that the researcher can exercise discretion in the manner in which he or she writes the texts. Researchers may opt to write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and employing qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of this study, the researcher shall utilize the first person in the understanding of how reading teachers implement individualized reading intervention for struggling readers.

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premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research was that the everyday world was a valuable and productive source of knowledge. By analyzing how an event oc-

curs daily, we could learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into its nature (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which was concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), I was projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study shall adopt a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design, since it focuses on the lived experiences of reading teachers handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data shall be read and reread, and culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher shall be able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and shall arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data, and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing was used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking of notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design

is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were useful for follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as further investigating their responses. In this qualitative research, interviews was used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees will say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher shall transcribe and type the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher shall collect data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis shall involve triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements shall be transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement shall fall under specific

psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations will be tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it shall be experienced. The researcher shall incorporate his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report shall be written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The re-

searcher needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations were to be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches shall be based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, emphasizing the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they would be a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of the teachers, the researcher intends to employ the phenomenological type of qualitative research.

2.4. Research Participants—This study should involve ten (10) reading teachers from the elementary schools of Banaybanay District, Division of Davao Oriental. The participants should be selected using the following inclusion criteria: (1) must have been a reading teacher or reading coordinator for the last five (five) years, and (2) must have handled individualized reading intervention for at least two (two) years. To determine the study's participants, the researcher should utilize the purposive sampling

design in as much as the participants should be picked with reference to the criteria or purpose of the study. This is in keeping with Creswell's (2014) notion that a purposive sampling technique is applicable in choosing a sample based on the criteria set and the data that the researcher wants to obtain for the study. This sampling technique was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective, as the selection of the participants should be purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Data Collection—To obtain the data needed to substantiate the study and respond to the questions raised, I conformed to the following procedures for data gathering. Precautionary measures and risk-prevention strategies shall also be applied whenever warranted by the situation. The following step-by-step process were used to gather the data needed. Sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher shall seek approval from

the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the elementary schools identified. I asked the Schools Division Superintendent through a letter and informed the said authority of the nature of the study by attaching Chapters 1 and 2 along with the research instrument. The study's objectives and the participants' identification should also be articulated. Only upon the approval of the superintendent can the data-gathering commence. Asking for Permission

from the School Heads. After securing the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher should write to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their school and seeking approval for its conduct. Obtaining Consent from the participants. Before gathering data from the participants, I should be informed of the nature of the research and the purposes it wants to serve. Likewise, they should be made to understand that data gathering would only proceed upon their consent. The researcher should also conduct a brief orientation on how the participants go about the in-depth interview process. Conducting the interview. Guided by the interview questionnaire, I should facilitate the in-depth interview. I should also note the profiles of the participants. As the interview goes on, I should jot down notes and record the conversations using an audio recorder for easy transcription. Also, I

should carefully listen and respond actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data should be categorized and coded. This should be followed by extracting themes and comparing and contrasting individual participant data. I then should conduct a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needs further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered should also be examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data would be compared and contrasted among the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The study should utilize a thematic analysis to analyze the data elicited from the participants in response to the questions they should ask during the in-depth interviews. I should adopt the data analysis model developed by Creswell (2012), who pointed out that themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. In qualitative research, familiarization with the data is a general notion common to all qualitative analysis forms. Thus, the researcher should immerse herself in data analysis and become adequately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. As to the coding of data as an approach to operationalize qualitative analysis, I should generate concise labels for important features of the data relevant to the research questions, which are generally broad. This should provide guidance to the analysis. In as much as coding does not only mean a method of data reduction but also an analytic

process, the code definitely facilitates either a semantic or conceptual reading of the data. Subscribing to this notion, as a researcher, I should code every data item and terminate this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes. With reference to the research questions, I should look for coherent and meaningful patterns in the data. I should also conclude this phase by collating all the coded data, considering its relevance to each theme. Reviewing themes. I should thoroughly review the identified themes and verify whether or not they tell a convincing and compelling story about the data. This process should begin with defining the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. In defining and naming themes, I should prepare a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying its essence and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up should involve weaving together the analytic narratives and data extracts to communicate to the readers

a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in line with the literature gathered. As a researcher, I should ensure that the experiences of the reading teachers implementing an individualized reading intervention are presented comprehensively.

2.7. *Analytical Framework*—The framework analysis of this research is made flexible as this permits the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or opt to perform data analysis as data collection is in progress. In the analysis stage, the gathered data shall be sifted, charted, and sorted in accordance with key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: familiarization, identifying a thematic framework, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected in such a way interview or focus group transcripts, observation or field notes and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, a mix of methods, such as interviews, documents, and observations, could be used. The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts, and themes that have been expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data gathered, including from the transcripts of interviews. For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher is cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994:186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations the researcher made echoed the participants’ true attitudes, beliefs, and values.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the data that were analyzed and discusses these data in relation to the research questions. Data presented and discussed in this section are basically the

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

participants’ responses as they disclosed their experiences in handling interventions for struggling readers. The reading teachers’ experiences, the coping mechanisms they adopted as they dealt with challenging experiences, and the educational insights that were drawn from these experiences are elaborated in this chapter.

Experiences of teachers in individualized Reading intervention for struggling readers

Teachers’ experiences in individualized reading intervention for struggling readers highlight the importance of personalized, data-driven instruction, flexibility, and a supportive learning environment. Common to all, the re-

sults of the study in line with this phenomenon reveal that success often comes from a combination of effective strategies, ongoing assessment, and a commitment to meeting the unique needs of each student.

3.0.1. Motivation and Engagement—Most reading teachers handling intervention for struggling readers were basically beset with the challenge brought about by a lower level of motivation and engagement of struggling readers. These learners are basically less motivated and engaged in the intervention, which can be explained by the learning shortcomings and the lack of skills that have affected the way they see reading. This is consistent with the findings of Snowling and Hulme (2015) as cited

in Brooks (2016), that children’s response to intervention may pose a challenge to reading instruction, children who respond poorly to literacy intervention tend to have oral language weaknesses and that it is possible to improve oral language skills by interventions focusing on developing listening skills, vocabulary and narrative skills. Developing vocabulary skills can be particularly effective and this is especially true both for those learning English as an additional language (Baker et al, 2014) and for older students.

3.0.2. Lack of Parental Involvement—

Building strong communication and collaboration with parents or caregivers is crucial in individualized interventions. Some parents may not be actively involved, making supporting the child's reading progress outside of school challenging. In this regard, the Center for Effective

Services (2016) sees parental involvement in reading interventions for struggling learners as crucial to a child's educational success. However, this does not seem to be a reality in the setup where the interviewed participants are situated.

3.0.3. Lack of Professional Development—The lack of professional development stands as a critical factor influencing the efficacy of individualized reading intervention programs for struggling readers. In the field of education, particularly in literacy instruction, ongoing professional development plays a pivotal role in equipping educators with the knowledge, skills, and strategies necessary to address the diverse needs of students, particularly those who struggle with reading. Without adequate training and support, educators may lack proficiency in identifying the specific learning challenges faced by struggling readers, as well as implementing evidence-based intervention strategies tailored to their unique needs. Furthermore, the absence of professional development opportunities may hinder educators' ability to stay abreast of the

latest research findings and best practices in reading instruction, limiting their capacity to effectively design and deliver individualized interventions that promote literacy development. Consequently, the lack of professional development can impede the quality and consistency of reading interventions, potentially exacerbating reading difficulties and hindering students' academic progress. Addressing this challenge requires a concerted effort to prioritize and invest in ongoing professional development initiatives that empower educators with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to support struggling readers effectively. Through targeted training, mentorship, and collaborative learning experiences, educators can enhance their capacity to deliver high-quality individualized reading interventions that meet the diverse needs of all learners.

3.1. Coping mechanisms of the reading teachers Handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers—Teachers who handle individualized reading intervention for struggling readers have undeniably come across several experiences that would seem to upset them as they, too, have to deal with all other functions related to instruction on top of their duties and responsibilities as teachers. Thus, in order to thrive in such a work environment where they are multi-tasked, these teachers adopt coping mechanisms to help them go through difficult times in the performance of their functions as regular teachers and concurrently as reading intervention teachers.

3.1.1. Patience and Empathy—The affective side of teachers handling individualized instruction to struggling readers is touched as they attend to their tasks as reading facilitators and encounter face-to-face with children needing their attention. Reading teachers in this context have come across learners' experiences that

appeal to their sense of compassion. As these reading teachers work with struggling readers, they may seem to lose patience as students under individualized instruction can hardly read and cope with the reading demands. Confronted with experiences like these some teachers may easily give up if they are confronted with sim-

Fig. 3. The Emerging Themes on the Experiences of Teachers in Individualized Reading Intervention for Struggling Readers

ilar situations. While others seem to lose patience and empathy to promote the reader’s welfare (Spector, 2018). patience, some teachers broaden their minds about the reading problem and develop an attitude of

3.1.2. Incorporating Technology—Most of the teachers handling individualized reading for struggling readers have strategized in the process of intervention to get things done with the expected efficiency and effectiveness. Although most of them have encountered several problems that would deter the goals of teaching reading, others have equipped themselves with the skill in the adoption and sustainability of the program by finding ways to make the job easier,

lighter and more manageable. One of the things that they do in order to minimize stress and difficulties is to incorporate technology in the reading intervention process. Some studies cited, including that of Crowley (2016) revealed that it is fundamental that teachers who are in such a reading instructional context would heavily rely upon technology. In this context, the use of reading materials includes software and programs that contain reading instruction and assessment of reading outcomes in digital forms.

3.1.3. Differentiation—With the belief that a struggling reader with a specific need is assessed, differentiating instruction was crucial in improving the reading skills of those struggling with reading. Differentiation in this context means designing reading instruction tailored to the reader’s specific needs. Many reading teachers in this context apply varied ways of addressing the reading needs of struggling readers. Dalto (2018) cited that reading teachers

not only facilitate reading instruction but also engage in the design and plan for reading that is relevant to the needs of struggling readers. Thus, in this context, children who are at this reading level are taught reading differently and are allotted much more time than teachers allotted to independent readers. Struggling readers often read less, have less exposure to print, and have limited sight vocabulary (Rief and Stern, 2015).

Fig. 4. The Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanisms of the Reading Teachers Handling Individualized Reading Intervention for Struggling Readers

3.2. *Educational insights gained from the experiences of the informants*—The following educational insights drawn from the participants’ narratives are crucial in a qualitative research undertaking. This part of the study outlines these insights as reflective of the views and perspectives on the issues at hand. Some of the participants’ revelations and contemplations were significant factors in reading development. Some of the participants cited the following insights from their experiences.

3.2.1. *Individual differences matter*—Differences in learners’ performance in terms of reading provide the dynamics for reading instruction. In this regard, so long as differences among learners exist, variation in their reading performance also exists. Hence, in this regard, Snowling and Hulme (2015), cited in Brooks (2016) note that children who respond poorly to

literacy intervention tend to have oral language weaknesses and that it is possible to improve oral language skills by interventions focusing on developing listening skills, vocabulary and narrative skills. This implies further that some other learners may not be able to exhibit the same ability. Hence, it is important that a reading teacher intervenes in reading by understanding individual differences.

3.2.2. *Early intervention is crucial*—The study participants are unanimous in considering the value of early intervention in addressing the reading needs of a struggling reader. They all have agreed that the earlier the detection of the reading problem, the better the reading needs can be catered. Along this line, Robson et al. (2016) emphasized the value of early interven-

tion as a driver of the success of the intervention. He further rationalized that early intervention allows the reading teacher to earlier address the problem with the idea that if it is not acted upon outright, reading problems will lead to complications that involve one’s total withdrawal from any reading activity, hence losing their chances to thrive in the academic and professional world.

3.2.3. *Parental and Community Involvement*—

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Gained from the Experiences of the Informants

One of the insights drawn by the participants from their experience is the impact of parental and community involvement as the individualized reading intervention is carried out. The participants cited that when parents or the community express gestures of collaboration through shared accountability of the reading progress of the learner, it motivates both the struggling reader and the teacher. Hence, along

this line, Rochford (2016) in a review by the Centre for Effective Services, noted that when engaging parents, often a key feature was the delivery of parent training sessions within the school buildings, thus improving accessibility and connectedness between school and home, thereby making the services better and are helpful in the process.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, and from the summary of the findings, the implications and future directions are drawn. My study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the reading teachers who have handled individualized reading interventions for struggling readers, unravel the coping mechanisms they adopted to address the challenges in the intervention and draw insights from these experiences. A qualitative phenomenological method was utilized, along with thematic analysis, to analyze the data to achieve the research objectives. The study adheres to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines in which open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their own definition or meaning of the explored phenomenon.

4.1. Findings—The study found that the experiences of the reading teachers handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers include low motivation and engagement, lack of professional development, and lack of parental involvement. In terms of the coping mechanisms of the reading teachers

handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers, the study found that these teachers demonstrated patience and empathy, applied differentiation, and incorporated technology to cope with the challenges all there were in the process of the conduct of the reading intervention. As to the educational manage-

ment insights gained from the participants, the study unraveled that teachers handling individualized reading intervention found that individual differences matter, and early intervention is

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on teachers' experiences handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers, the interview results revealed the following themes: First, there was low motivation and engagement. This experience of reading teachers tells us that they get upset in the conduct of the intervention as motivation from and engagement with the community is deemed minimal. Second, there was a lack of professional development. Teachers handling individualized reading intervention believed that they could hardly carry out their assigned tasks as they lacked training in the intervention process. Third is the lack of parental involvement. Teachers handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers were at times upset that parents' involvement in the process was generally low. On the coping mechanisms of teachers handling individualized reading intervention to struggling readers, one of the themes that emerged is that patience and empathy truly matter. These teachers believed that showing compassion and empathy to the struggling reader helps them cope with all the challenges in the intervention. The second theme regarding the

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that all concerned should address the specific experiences that hinder teachers from handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers. The success of the intervention equates with the teachers' capability to deal with these experiences. This study may provide an avenue

crucial. Parental and community involvement were relevant insights drawn forth from these experiences.

coping mechanism teachers use to handle individualized reading intervention for struggling readers is differentiation. Adopting differentiated instruction specially designed for struggling readers helped them cope with the challenges related to the intervention. The third theme that emerged was incorporating technology. Teachers handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers found that it is important that they incorporate technology in the context of reading intervention to get the desired reading outcomes. The educational management insights gained from the teachers handling individualized reading intervention for struggling readers revealed the first theme: Individual differences matter in the intervention process. The participants believed that the intervention could be relevant and meaningful once these differences were considered. The second theme that emerged is that early intervention is crucial. In the intervention process, most of the participants cited that early intervention addressing the reading needs of the learner allows ample time to cater to the needs of the struggling reader. The third theme that emerged was that parental and community involvement is crucial in the process. This involvement has a positive impact on both the reader and the teacher.

to enlighten the school heads to continue supporting their teachers in handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers in the assignment of the teaching loads. School heads may consider the workload of these reading teachers and assist them in providing technical assistance and other support that would continue to inspire these teachers to walk the

extra mile in reading instruction. Teachers who provide individualized reading intervention to struggling readers must also continuously seek professional advancement through attendance in training and other capability-building ventures. This will adequately equip them to better their services. The school community should likewise recognize the contributions of teachers who provide individualized reading intervention to struggling readers, as this inspires them to carry out the program. Similar studies may be conducted in other regions or divisions for future researchers. The researchers may consider other aspects of the experiences of the teachers handling individualized reading interventions for struggling readers

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